

A STUDY OF CONSUMER PERCEPTION OVER THE ONLINE FOOD DELIVERY APPS WITH REFERENCE TO NAGPUR CITY

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Abstract

The effect of internet, e-commerce industry, innovation and customers expectations fall on the hotel industry as well. After taking the need and expectations of customers into consideration the online food delivery applications come into existence. These online food delivery apps are committed to provide the quality services, save their time, provide concession, discounts and offers to the customers. The online food delivery application is getting success to attract young generation by offering various services and facilities. Apart from the popularity of the online food delivery application there are many customers who do not want to use online food delivery services. They still want to go personally in restaurants, enjoy their meal, and enjoy the ambience and atmosphere.

The objective of this paper is to know the reasons why online food delivery application are getting popular, satisfaction level of the customers after using apps, challenges faced by the customers at the time using apps, the factors affect the customers that influence to use online food delivery apps. This study is based on the primary data which has collected through the structured questioner collected from the 288 respondents of Nagpur city selected randomly. The study is also considered secondary data collected from the newspapers, websites, research papers, online applications etc.

This research paper tried to throw the light on the factors which influence the customers to use online foods delivery apps, their age, their online buying behavior and on the same time the factors which do support the personally visit the restaurants and enjoy the food.

Keywords: Online Food Delivery, Perception of Consumers, Online Services, Quality of Food, Expectations of the customers.

Introduction

Now a days there is rapid changes can seen in the technology due to innovation, competition and expectation of the users. Due changes in technology, new systems, new application, new uses come in front which saves the time, cost and efforts. The online food delivery app is one of the innovations of technology which is helpful to save cost, efforts and time of the consumer. Online food delivery apps provide the facility to enjoy the food from any restaurant by simply online ordering and without visiting to that particular restaurant. With the use of online food delivery apps the customers can order any food that they like to eat at that particular time from any place of the city, which helps to save time, efforts and cost to visit.

The popularity of the online food delivery apps is increasing day by day due to various reasons and factors. The online food delivery apps trying to attract customers by providing various offers, discounts, customization of services, premium services etc. The youngsters, techno-savy persons, bachelors, busy persons are using these apps very frequently. This paper is trying to understand the reason of increasing the popularity of online food delivery apps, experiences of the customers, quality of food provided by online food delivery apps, their services and expectations of the customers.

There are many online food delivery apps that are providing valuable services to the customers. Swiggy, Zomato, Dunzo, Domino's, EatSute, FreshMenu, TravelKhana, Tapzu, Homeffodi etc. online food delivery apps are working in India and providing online food ordering services. Such apps are offering discount and offers, influencer marketing and referral programme for acquisition more and more customers. Personalization recommendation, loyalty programme and real time tracking system are some strategies adopted by online food delivery apps for customer retentions. The online food delivery apps are getting popularity in the youngster.

Apart from the using online food delivery apps there are many customers who want to go personally in restaurant to enjoy their food. Most of the people generally want to visit restaurant and enjoy their food. They do not want to

enjoy their food only but they want to feel it's ambiance, atmospheres etc. Personally visit to restaurant increase the quality time by meeting friends and relative at same place, discuss with them, sharing of thoughts and emotions etc.

Literature Review

The present research paper reviewed the following literatures:

D. Neduraman and M. Madhuritha in 2023 written a research paper on “**Customer Attitude Towards Online food Delivery Apps: An Practical Approach**”: In their research paper they focused on increasing popularity of online food apps, features of online food apps, consumer attitude towards the online food delivery apps. They have taken opinion of 50 respondents for their study. They have selected 50 respondents on random basis. Frequency distribution descriptive statistics, Chi-Square Analysis and Garrett ranking are used by them for drawing the conclusion. As per conclusion of their research paper there are many factors which influence consumers to use online food delivery apps. The food delivery companies need to maintain competitive edge and to understand the ever changing consumer behavior.

Mohak Jain and Paresh Patel in 2024 written a research paper on “**A Study on Consumer Behavior Towards Online Food Ordering with Reference to Gujrat**”: In their research paper they focused on influencing factors before ordering food online, buying habit of consumer while ordering food online, preferable mode of payment and growth and trend of online food delivery services. Their paper was based on the primary as well as secondary data. In Primary data they have taken the opinions from the consumers of various districts of Gujarat. They have used convenient sampling method to collect the data. As per their conclusion the consumers are highly satisfied with the online delivery apps. The quality of food from online food delivery apps is the one of the important factors to which affect significantly.

Nada Jaboor Al Maalouf, Elie Sayegh, Wissam Makhoul and Nada Sarkis in 2024 written a research paper on “**Consumer Attitude and Purchase Intensions towards Food Ordering via Online Platforms**”: In their research paper they focused on quality of e-services, personal aspects, quality of food, trust, time saving orientation, convenience, positive attitude towards the online food delivery services all these factors affect on behavior towards the online food delivery. Their research paper was based on the primary data. They have collected the responses from 280 customers. They have used chi-square test to draw the conclusions. As per their conclusion they suggested to hotel business to improve the quality and dining experience to remain competitive with online food delivery.

Dr. P. PirakaTheeswari and Ezhilarasan A. in 2024 written a research paper on “**A Study on Consumer Preferences towards Online Food Delivery App with references to Coimbatore City**”: In their research paper they focused on awareness of food delivery apps, preferences towards online food ordering, services provided by online food delivery apps and problem faced by the consumers while using online delivery apps. They have collected the data by using primary method of data collection. Their sample size was 123 respondents. They have used percentage analysis, Chi-Square analysis and Rank analysis to draw the conclusions. As per their conclusion the factors like user interface, restaurant selection and delivery timing influence the choice of consumers. Apart from this the menu display, ordering tracking system, user profile customization etc. enhance the consumer experience and meet consumer experience.

Shwetha Pai and Sureshramana Mayya in 2022 written a research paper on “**A Study on Consumer Preferences with reference to Online Food Delivery Amenities**”: In their research paper they focused on consumer preferences and perception about online food delivery amenities, identify the elements that impact the consumer decisions, obstacles faced by the consumers while using online food delivery amenities etc. They have collected the data from the primary source where they collected data of 168 respondents. They have used SPSS software to analyze the data and to draw the conclusions. As per their conclusion they said the consumer perception and preferences changes due to various factors like personal preference, tastes, lifestyle and similarities. The online food delivery apps are increasing gain, trust, loyalty, integrity and retention of customers due to best and fastest services.

Research Gap

There are many researches done on the online food delivery applications out of these above some research papers are taken for literature review based on the keywords. All the above research paper mainly focused on the factors which affect the consumer to use the online food delivery apps, the offers and schemes provided by the online apps to attract more customers and expectations of the customers. But most of the papers are lacking to studies on why the customer still prefer visit to the restaurants personally. These papers do not cover the expectation and reasons of personally visit the restaurants. Apart from the facilities and services offered by the online food delivery apps the services and offers provided by the restaurants are taken into consideration in the present study.

Research Methodology

The present study is explorative and descriptive in nature. This study is based on the primary data to collect about the perception of general public on online food delivery apps through structured questioners on Google form. For understanding and explaining the concepts and feature of online food delivery apps secondary data has been used.

a. Sample Design and Size:

- i. The targeted population of the study is people of Nagpur city.
- ii. A total number of 288 people of various areas of Nagpur city selected randomly.

b. Tools Used:

The conclusion of the study has been drawn by using frequency analysis, percentage and T-test using SPSS software.

Objectives

The present research paper is based on the following objectives:

1. To study the consumer perceptions about online food delivery apps.
2. To understand the consumer satisfaction level by using online food delivery apps.
3. To study the facilities and services provided by various online food delivery apps.
4. To know the challenges faced by the consumers while using online food delivery apps.
5. To know the factors influences the consumers to buy through online food delivery apps.
6. To know the reasons of increasing popularity of online food delivery apps.

Hypothesis:

Hypothesis: 1

H0: Online food delivery apps are not helpful to save time as well as cost of food.

H1: Online food delivery apps are helpful to save time as well as cost of food.

Hypothesis: 2

H0: The satisfaction level of consumer after using online food delivery apps is not high.

H1: The satisfaction level of consumer after using online food delivery apps is high.

Hypothesis: 3

H0: Online food delivery apps are not providing better services as well as facilities to consumers.

H1: Online food delivery apps are providing better services as well as facilities to consumers.

Hypothesis: 4

H0: Consumers do not face the challenges and difficulties at the time of using online food delivery apps.

H1: Consumers face the challenges and difficulties at the time of using online food delivery apps.

Hypothesis: 5

H0: Various schemes offered by online food delivery apps do not attract consumer to use it.

H1: Various schemes offered by online food delivery apps attract consumer to use it.

Hypothesis: 6

H0: The popularity of online food delivery apps are not increasing day by day.

H1: The popularity of online food delivery apps are increasing day by day.

Hypothesis: 7

H0: Online food delivery apps are not become the alternatives for dinning out in hotels.

H1: Online food delivery apps become the alternatives for dinning out in hotels.

Limitations:

The present research paper has following limitations:

1. The present research is based on selected online food delivery apps.
2. This paper considered the opinions of the consumers of Nagpur city only.
3. This study is restricted with limited number of respondents.
4. This study considered limited number of literature review.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

The data collected from the 288 customers through structured questioner. The collected responses are tabulated and t-test has applied for hypothesis testing as per following manner:

Table No. 1: Online food delivery apps are helpful to save time as well as cost of food.

Responses	No. of Respondents
Strongly Agree	89
Agree	91
Disagree	65
Strongly Disagree	43
Total	288

Interpretation: The above table shows the responses received regarding how online food delivery apps is helpful to save the time and cost of food. As per the responses 89 respondents are strongly agree that the online food delivery apps is helpful to save cost and time both. The 91 respondents responded that they are agreeing on the statements. 65 respondents are disagreeing on that the online food delivery apps are helpful to save the time and cost whereas 43 respondents are strongly disagree over the statement.

$$\text{Mean} = (89 \times 1) + (91 \times 2) + (65 \times 3) + (43 \times 4) = 638 / 288 = 2.22$$

$$\text{S.D.} = 1.04$$

$$\mu = 2$$

$$t(\text{cal.}) = 3.49$$

$$t(\text{tab}) = 1.96$$

As per the calculation $t(\text{cal.}) > t(\text{tab.})$ hence the null hypothesis i.e. Online food delivery apps are not helpful to save time as well as cost of food is rejected. It means the online food delivery apps are in position to save the time and cost of food. This is possible because the personally visit to any restaurants take at least two hours the time to go and come back. But the average delivery time of food from placing the order till receiving the delivery is 30 to 35 min. hence, most of the respondents feel that the average time of going to the restaurant is more as compare with the apps. The cost of charging for the food by online food delivery apps is quit cheaper than the cost offering by the restaurants. The online food delivery offers some amount of discount and concession as well.

Table No. 2: The satisfaction level of consumer after using online food delivery apps is high.

Responses	No. of Respondents
Strongly Agree	120
Agree	85
Disagree	48
Strongly Disagree	35
Total	288

Interpretation: The above table is representing the responses collected over the satisfaction level of consumer over the functioning of online food delivery apps. As per the tabulated data 120 respondents are strongly agree over the online food delivery apps are providing satisfaction to them. 85 respondents are of the opinion that they are agreeing on the statement. 48 respondents are disagreeing on that online food delivery apps are providing satisfaction to them whereas only 35 respondents are strongly disagree over the statement.

$$\text{Mean} = (120 \times 1) + (85 \times 2) + (48 \times 3) + (35 \times 4) = 574 / 288 = 1.99$$

$$\text{S.D.} = 1.04$$

$$\mu = 1$$

$$t(\text{cal.}) = 16.23$$

$$t(\text{tab}) = 1.96$$

As per the calculation $t(\text{cal.}) > t(\text{tab.})$ it means the null hypothesis i.e. The satisfaction level of consumer after using online food delivery apps is not high is rejected.

The most of the consumer feel that the online food delivery apps are useful to save the time and cost of them. It directly indicates that the consumers are satisfied over the overall functioning of the online food delivery apps. The quality of food, test, delivery time etc. factors are also affected over the satisfaction level of the consumer. The quality of food provided by online food delivery apps is good and the customers can give some cooking instruction at the time of placing the order. The age of the consumer, frequency of online food ordering and expectations of the consumers etc. are also some factors which influence the consumer's satisfaction level.

Table No. 3: Online food delivery apps are providing better services as well as facilities to consumers.

Responses	No. of Respondents
Strongly Agree	93
Agree	88
Disagree	74
Strongly Disagree	33
Total	288

Interpretation: This table is representing the responses collected from the consumers regarding the services as well as facilities providing by the online food delivery apps. As per the responses 93 respondents are strongly agreeing that the services and facilities providing by the online food delivery apps are better than the personally going to the restaurant. 88 respondents are agreeing to the statement. Only 33 respondents are strongly disagree that the services and facilities of online food delivery apps are not better than the personal visit to the restaurant where are 74 respondents said they are disagree over the statement.

$$\text{Mean} = (93 \times 1) + (88 \times 2) + (74 \times 3) + (33 \times 4) = 623 / 288 = 2.16$$

$$\text{S.D.} = 1.00$$

$$\mu = 1$$

$$t(\text{cal.}) = 19.66$$

$$t(\text{tab}) = 1.96$$

As per the calculation $t(\text{cal.}) > t(\text{tab.})$ it means the null hypothesis i.e. Online food delivery apps are not providing better services as well as facilities to consumers is rejected. Selection of quantity, add cooking instruction, selection of the restaurants, online tracking systems are such services makes the online food delivery apps as a perfect choice for the customers. The discount facilities, rewards system and attractive offers are much effective to attract more and more customers to order the food through online food delivery apps. The most of the consumer now prefer to order food through online food delivery apps due to services offered by them.

Table No. 4: Consumers face the challenges and difficulties at the time of using online food delivery apps.

Responses	No. of Respondents
Strongly Agree	55
Agree	43
Disagree	87
Strongly Disagree	103
Total	288

Interpretation: The above table is showing the responses of consumers over the any difficulties and challenges faced by the consumer while ordering the food online through apps. The 55 responded that they have faced the difficulties at the time of online food ordering whereas 43 respondents responded that they are agreeing over the statement. 103 respondents strongly agree that they have faced the challenges whereas 87 respondents said they are agreeing on the statement.

$$\text{Mean} = (55 \times 1) + (43 \times 2) + (87 \times 3) + (103 \times 4) = 814 / 288 = 2.83$$

$$\text{S.D.} = 1.11$$

$$\mu = 4$$

$$t(\text{cal.}) = 18.00$$

$$t(\text{tab}) = 1.96$$

As per the above calculation $t(\text{cal.}) > t(\text{tab.})$ it means the null hypothesis i.e. Consumers do not face the challenges and difficulties at the time of using online food delivery apps is rejected. The apps made by the online food delivery companies so well that any confusion about the ordering the food is automatically solved. But still the average customers having less knowledge about operation of apps may face the difficulties at the time of operating apps. The customers generally face the problem at the time of selecting restaurant nearby them. Selection of dish and its quantity may be some time become problematic. Major issues face by the customers at the time of online payment via using various online payment applications. After ordering the food most of the time delivery person does not get the proper address given by the customer and most of the time go waste while making him understand the exact location.

Table No. 5: Various schemes offered by online food delivery apps attract consumer to use it.

Responses	No. of Respondents
Strongly Agree	74
Agree	111
Disagree	63
Strongly Disagree	40
Total	288

Interpretation: The above table is representing the views of general public on the various schemes offered by the online food delivery apps to attract the customers. 74 customers responded that they are agreeing that the online food delivery apps are providing various schemes to them for attracting. The 111 responded are of the opinion that they are agree with the statement. 63 customers feel that the schemes offered by the apps cannot attract to order the food through using the online apps whereas 40 respondents are strongly disagreeing on the statement.

$$\text{Mean} = (74 \times 1) + (111 \times 2) + (63 \times 3) + (40 \times 4) = 645 / 288 = 2.24$$

$$\text{S.D.} = 0.99$$

$$\mu = 2$$

$$t(\text{cal.}) = 4.14$$

$$t(\text{tab}) = 1.96$$

As per the calculation $t(\text{cal.}) > t(\text{tab.})$ it means the null hypothesis i.e. Various schemes offered by online food delivery apps do not attract consumer to use it is rejected. Most of the customers always want to get the food from the restaurant s at the cheapest rate. The cheapest rate in not possible at the time of personal visit because the restaurants do not offer and discount on bill and customers need to give some amount of money to the service provider as tip as well. But online food delivery applications offer various types of discounts. First order discount, repeat order discount, discount to premium customers. Such discount helps to save lots of money of the customers. Such discounts and offers help the online food delivery companies to attract more customers and retain them as well.

Table No. 6: The popularity of online food delivery apps are increasing day by day.

Responses	No. of Respondents
Strongly Agree	102
Agree	77
Disagree	49
Strongly Disagree	60
Total	288

Interpretation: The above table is representing the opinions of customers over the popularity of the online food delivery apps. The 102 respondents are the opinion that they are strongly agree over the statement that the popularity of online apps is increasing. 77 respondents said they are agreeing on the statement. 49 respondents are of the opinion that the popularity of the online food delivery apps in not increasing whereas 60 respondents are totally denied the statement.

$$\text{Mean} = (102 \times 1) + (77 \times 2) + (49 \times 3) + (60 \times 4) = 643 / 288 = 2.23$$

$$\text{S.D.} = 1.14$$

$$\mu = 2$$

$$t(\text{cal.}) = 3.43$$

$$t(\text{tab.}) = 1.96$$

As per the calculation $t(\text{cal.}) < t(\text{tab.})$ it means the null hypothesis i.e. The popularity of online food delivery apps are not increasing day by day is rejected. The online food delivery apps are trying to attract young consumers to buy online via offering various schemes and concessions. The online food delivery apps are more popular in youngster as well as all age customers and because of the service, facilities and quality of food provided by them. Due to save of time, cost and efforts in fast moving world these apps are getting popularity over the traditional dinning out culture.

Table No. 7: Online food delivery apps become the alternatives for dinning out in hotels.

Responses	No. of Respondents
Strongly Agree	66
Agree	34
Disagree	88
Strongly Disagree	100
Total	288

Interpretation: This table is showing the responses collected about whether online food delivery apps become the alternatives for dinning out or not. As per the responses collected 66 respondents are of the opinion of they are strongly agreeing on the statement that online food delivery apps are become alternative for dinning out. 34 respondents said they are agreeing on the statement. 88 respondents are the opinion that they disagreeing the statement whereas 100 respondents are strongly disagreed on the statement.

$$\text{Mean} = (66 \times 1) + (34 \times 2) + (88 \times 3) + (100 \times 4) = 798 / 288 = 2.77$$

$$\text{S.D.} = 1.15$$

